

Formidlingsaktivitet

Art: SDU FysikLab Science Workshop

Sted: Odense / SDU / SDU-Galaxy

Skole: Inst. f. Naturfagernes Didaktik / Københavns Universitet

Dato: 10. September 2024

Tid: 13:00 – 16:30

Antal elever: ca. 13.

GDPR / pictures for public? Yes. I asked and obtained permission.

Lærerkontakt: Dr. Magdalena Kersting (University of Copenhagen)

Formidler: Tobias C. Hinse & Pernille Troung (SDU / FKF / SDU-Galaxy)

Missing from the picture: Pernille Troung (SDU / FKF / SDU-Galaxy)

